

PANCHAKARMA-BASED MANAGEMENT OF APABAHUKA CORRESPONDING TO PARSONAGE–TURNER SYNDROME: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Apabahuka* is a *Vataja* disorder causing pain, stiffness, and dysfunction of the upper limb due to involvement of the *Amsa mula* region. Clinically, it correlates with Parsonage–Turner syndrome, characterized by acute shoulder pain followed by neurological deficits and muscle atrophy. **Aim:** To evaluate the role of *Ayurvedic Panchakarma* therapy in the management of *Apabahuka* with reference to Parsonage–Turner syndrome. **Materials and Methods:** This single-case study was conducted at Sri Kalabyraveswarswamy Ayurvedic Medical College, Bengaluru. A 36-year-old male with left upper limb weakness, tremors, and muscle atrophy was diagnosed with *Apabahuka* w.s.r. to Parsonage–Turner syndrome based on clinical findings and nerve conduction studies. The patient received a structured Panchakarma regimen comprising *Greeva Basti*, *Sarvanga Abhyanga*, *Sarvanga Pariseka*, *Shashtika Shali Pinda Sweda*, *Nasya*, and *Nasapana*, followed by internal medications. Outcomes were assessed using muscle power, muscle bulk, range of motion, and functional ability. **Results:** Post-treatment, the patient showed improvement in muscle strength (grade 3 to 4), reduction in muscle twitching, improved shoulder symmetry, and reversal of infraspinatus muscle atrophy, with significant functional recovery. **Conclusion:** This case suggests that *Panchakarma*-based approach was effective in managing *Apabahuka* corresponding to Parsonage–Turner syndrome, indicating its potential role in neuropathic shoulder disorders.

KEYWORDS: *Apabahuka*, Parsonage Turner Syndrome, *Nasya*, *Nasapana*, *Shashtika Shali Pinda Sweda*, *Panchakarma*.

INTRODUCTION

Apabahuka is a disease, which impairs the normal functioning of the upper limb. The prefix ‘*Apa*’ refers to *Viyoga*, or *Vikrutau*^[1] which means dysfunction or separation and *Bahuka* refers to arm. It can be summarised as dysfunction of *Bahu* or dysability in the arm. Vitiated *Vata* located at *Amsamula* (Brachial Plexus) causes *Sirah Sankocha* and produce *Apabahuka* which results in *Bahupraspanditahara*^[2] (*Praspandana* means movement or *chalana*). According to *Madhava Nidana*,

there are two conditions mentioned, *Amsa shosha* and *Apabahuka*. *Amsa shosha* can be considered as the preliminary stage of the disease where loss or dryness of the *Sleshaka Kapha* from the shoulder joint occurs. The next stage, *Apabahuka* occurs due to loss of *Sleshaka Kapha* and symptoms like *Shoola*, restricted range of motion. In *Madhukosha Teeka*, it is stated that *Amsa Shosha* is produced by *Dhatukshaya (Shuddha Vata Janya)* and *Apabahuka* is *Vata Kapha Janya*.^[3]

Nidana

There can be two types of *Hetu*:

1. *Bahya Hetu* – causes that lead to injury to *Marma* (especially *Amsa Marma* – *Snayu Marma*) or region surrounding that.
2. *Abhyantara Hetu* – *Dosha prakopajanya* – indulging in *Vata Prakopa*

Under the Umbrella of *Apabahuka*, the below may be considered:

- Adhesive Capsulitis
- Subacromial Bursitis/ Subcorocoid Bursitis
- Bicipital Tendonitis
- Brachial Plexus Neuropathy – Erb's Palsy/ Parsonage-Turner syndrome/ Klumpke's Palsy

A near co-relation to *Apabahuka* with respect to this case is Parsonage-Turner Syndrome. It has symptoms with abrupt onset of shoulder pain, usually unilateral followed by progressive neurologic deficits of motor weakness, dysesthesias, numbness. The pain may extend to trapezius ridge, upper arm, forearm and hand. The pain is usually worse at night.^[4] The patient may not immediately note the atrophic changes due to reluctance in using the affected hand. In this prospective cohort, patients with new onset neck/shoulder/arm complaints were screened, and neuralgic amyotrophy accounted for about 3% of such cases — roughly 1 per 1,000 new presentations.^[5]

Approximately 70% of Indians are employed in occupations involving agriculture, construction, and factory-based manual or skilled labour, which include construction workers, agricultural labourers, factory/assembly-line workers, electricians, painters, and loaders/porters. The people involved in these professions are prone to Repetitive shoulder abduction and external rotation, traction injury to upper trunk (C5–C6) and micro-ischemia of the plexus. The mainstay management for this condition revolves around opioids, NSAIDs, neuroleptics, TENS and oral steroids though recommended, there is poor literature evidence to support in efficacy. In this regard, this case serves as a valuable example of how Ayurvedic Panchakarma treatment can be effectively utilized in managing Parsonage-Turner Syndrome.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Centre of study

- SKAMCH & RC Vijaynagar, Bengaluru.
- Simple Random single case study.

CASE REPORT

A 36 year old male patient presented with chief complaints of weakness in left upper limb, stiffness and difficulty to lift weights in left upper limb since 3 months.

History of present illness: A 36 year old male patient, working as a car driver, was apparently healthy until

about 3 months ago. Patient initially had pain at the nape of neck 3 months back, for which he had consulted an orthopedician, an MRI of Cervical Spine was advised, which revealed disc herniation at C₅-C₆ and C₆-C₇. He was advised to undergo Interferential Therapy and exercises. After a period of 2 weeks, the pain in his nape of neck persisted and patient noticed a pea sized swelling in his shoulder. The Patient underwent spinal decompression therapy along with manual massage for 18 days, he was advised to undergo nerve conduction study, which indicated Left radial nerve motor neuropathy. Though initially patient responded with respect to range of motion of left upper limb, later on his symptoms worsened. He had difficulty in extending his elbow, weakness in left upper limb and tremors in his left upper limb while lifting objects, hence he had approached Panchakarma OPD of Sri Kalabyraveswary Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre Bengaluru, on examination patient had weakness in left upper limb and significant muscle atrophy was observed in infraspinatus muscle. Hence, he was admitted at the hospital for further management.

Past history: Patient was not a known case of Diabetes Mellitus or trauma over shoulder region.

Medical History: Prednisolone 20mg (1-0-1)

Family History: No history of musculoskeletal disorders in the family.

Personal history

- Diet- Mixed
- Appetite- Good
- Micturition - 3-4times /day, pale yellow
- Bowel - 1-2times /day regular, semisolid
- Sleep - Disturbed due to pain
- Habits- Nil

General Examination

- Appearance – Normal
- Built – Moderate
- Pallor – Absent
- Icterus – Absent
- Cyanosis – Absent
- Clubbing – Absent
- Lymphadenopathy – Absent
- Edema – Absent
- BP – 120/70 mmHg
- Pulse – 78/ min, regular
- Temp – 97.4°F

Systemic Examination

- CNS – Higher Mental unction intact, well oriented to time, place and person,
- CVS – S1, S2 heard, no murmurs detected in cardiovascular system,
- RS – NVBS heard Bilaterally, no added sounds,
- P/A - Soft, non – tender.

Aturabala Pramana Pareeksha

- Prakruti: Kapha Pittja
- Vikruti: Madhyama
- 1. Dosha: Vata pradhana tridosha
- 2. Dushya: Rasa, Rakta Mamsa
- 3. Prakruti: Vata
- 4. Desha: Sadharana
- 5. Kala: Sharad rtu
- Sara: Madhyama
- Samhanana: Madhyama
- Pramana : Madhyama (Height – 165cm, Weight – 72kg BMI - 26.4)

- Satmya: Vyamishra Madhyama
- Satva: Madhyama
- Aharashakthi: Abhyavaharanashakti: Madhyama; Jarana shakti: Madhyama
- Vyayamashakthi: Madhyama
- Vaya: Madhyama

Investigation

- Nerve Conduction Study revealed Left Radial Nerve Motor Neuropathy.

Table 1: Local Examination – Left Shoulder Joint.

Inspection	
1. Swelling	Absent
1. Discoloration	Absent
2. Deformities	Asymmetry of Shoulder
3. Muscle Atrophy	Wasting observed in infraspinatus muscle
Palpation	
1. Tenderness	Absent
2. Local Rise in Temperature	Absent
Range of Movements	
1. Flexion	180°
2. Extension	30°
3. Abduction	45°
4. Adduction	30°
5. Internal Rotation	70°
6. External Rotation	30°

Table 2: Motor Examination of Upper Limbs.

Motor Examination	Right	Left
1. Muscle tone	Normal	Normal
2. Muscle Power	5	3
3. Involuntary Movement	Absent	Muscle twitches observed while lifting objects
4. Muscle Bulk		
➤ Mid Arm Circumference	33 cm	30 cm
➤ Mid-Forearm Circumference	28 cm	25 cm
5. Deep Tendon Reflexes		
➤ Brachial Reflex	2+	2+
➤ Triceps Reflex	2+	1+
➤ Brachioradialis Reflex	2+	1+

Diagnosis – Apabahuka w.s.r to Parsonage-Turner Syndrome.

Treatment**Table 3: Treatment given to the patient.**

First Phase of treatment (1 st day - 5 th day) (9/11/2025 to 13/11/2025)	➤ Greeva Basti with Murchita Taila
	➤ Sarvanga Abyanga with Murchita Taila
	➤ Sarvanga Pariseka with Murchita Taila
	➤ Sthanika Shashtika Shali Pinda Sweda with Balamoola and Dashamoola Kashaya (Shoulder and upper limb)
	➤ Nasya Karma with Ksheerabala 101 Avarti (10 bindus in each nostril)
Second Phase of treatment (6 th day – 12 th day) (14/11/2025 to 20/11/25)	➤ Greeva Basti with Murchita Taila
	➤ Sarvanga Abyanga with Murchita Taila
	➤ Sarvanga Pariseka with Murchita Taila
	➤ Sthanika Shashtika Shali Pinda Sweda with Balamoola and

	Dashamoola Kashaya (Shoulder and upper limb)
➤	Baladi Mamsarasa Siddha Nasapana ^[6] (4.5ml to 5 ml in each nostril)

Follow up medication - (Advised for 15 days)

1. Baladi Mamsarasa Siddha Pratimarsha Nasya (2 bindus in each nostril)
2. Mamsyadi Kwatha (1tsp boiled with 100ml of water reduced to 30ml, 30ml-0-30ml)

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Table 4: Assessment chart of Upper Limb Motor Examination -Before and After.

Sl.No.	Before Treatment	After Treatment
1. Deformities	Shoulder asymmetry present	Improved Shoulder symmetry
2. Muscle Atrophy	Marked Wasting at Infraspinatus muscle	Significant improvement seen in Infraspinatus Muscle
3. Involuntary Movement	Muscle twitches – Present	Absent
4. Shoulder Flexion	180°	180°
5. Shoulder Extension	30°	40°
6. Shoulder Abduction	45°	60°
7. Internal Rotation	70°	80°
8. External Rotation	30°	50°
9. VAS	6	1

Significant reduction in the symptoms after treatment. Complaints of weakness in left upper limb, stiffness and difficulty to lift weights in left upper limb improved. The asymmetry and posture of shoulder and upper back improved. Muscle atrophy observed at infraspinatus had

visibly improved at the time of discharge and follow up. Muscle twitches seen during lifting weights (of about 500g to 1kg) by left upper limb had reduced completely. Muscle power increased from grade 3 to grade 4.

Image 1: Showing the atrophic changes at infraspinatus muscle 1. On the day of opd consultation. 2. On the day of discharge. 3. At the time of follow up (from left to right)

DISCUSSION

In routine clinical practice, Adhesive capsulitis and Parsonage–Turner syndrome are frequently confused because of common presenting symptoms. However, PTS typically begins with a sudden, severe, deep shoulder or upper arm pain, and frequently worse at night. This intense pain phase lasts for days to a few weeks and then subsides abruptly, after which the patient develops marked weakness of the shoulder girdle and upper arm muscles. Importantly, on examination, passive range of motion of the shoulder is largely preserved, even though active movements are weak. In contrast, adhesive capsulitis has a gradual and insidious onset. Pain develops slowly and is typically movement-related. The hallmark feature is restriction of both active and passive shoulder movements, especially external rotation, abduction, and flexion. Weakness in adhesive capsulitis is secondary to pain and stiffness, not true neurological weakness.

The severity of PTS can vary widely depending on extent of inflammatory damage to brachial plexus nerves, which can involve Neuropraxia (temporary conduction block) while mild cases might involve only neuropraxia and lead to rapid full recovery, many cases involve more severe Axonotmesis (axonal loss) which portends a longer and potentially less favourable recovery prognosis. The upper trunk of the brachial plexus, the suprascapular nerve, the long thoracic nerve, and the axillary nerves are the most commonly involved.

The main pathology involved here is due to *Dhatukshayajanya Vatavyadhi* and line of management should be adopted based on *Nirupastambhita vatavyahi chikitsa*. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt *Brimhana* line of management to relieve the symptoms caused due to *Apatarpana*.

When we look into the *Chikitsa of Apabahuka*

- *Ashtanga Sangraha* mentions *Navana Nasya* and *Snehapana*
- *Acharya Sushruta* advises *Vatavyadhi chikitsa* for *Apabahuka* except *Siravyadha*
- *Chikitsa Sara Sangraha* mentions *Nasya* and *Uttarabhaktika Snehapana*
- *Brimhana Nasya* is indicated in *Apabahuka* by *Vatavyadhi*

✚ *Greeva Basti* is a therapeutic procedure that incorporates both *snehana* and *swedana*. In this patient, the treatment was selected in view of the presence of intervertebral disc herniation. It is classified under *Shadvidha Upakrama* and falls within *Bahirparimarjana chikitsa*, specifically a retentive type of procedure. The rationale for selecting *Greeva Basti* lies in its direct application over the affected cervical region, allowing localized therapeutic action. Pathologies involving the cervical spine are commonly associated with structural alterations of the vertebral column, including derangement of cervical vertebrae and degenerative changes of the intervertebral discs. Additionally, impairment of the lubricating function of *Shleshaka Kapha* leads to increased friction, resulting in nerve compression and irritation, which manifests clinically as severe pain and muscle spasm. Hence, *Sthanika snehana* and *Swedana* through *Greeva Basti* is considered effective in alleviating pain, reducing muscle spasm, and improving local tissue nourishment.

✚ *Sarvanga Abhyanga* with *Murchita Taila* does *Vatashamana*, *Brimhana*, regulating the functions of *Vata* and *Kapha* and brings *Snehana* effect to the *Sandhi*. Patient's body attains *Dridatha* as well.

✚ *Sarvanaga Pariseka* with *Dashamula Kwatha*, *Seka* with *Dashamuula Kwatha* is mentioned as a treatment modality in managing *Vata* disorder in *Vatasya Upakrama*. To relieve symptoms like *Gatisanga*, *Stabdhatta*, *Dashamoola Kashaya Seka* which is *Vatakaphahara* is adopted.

✚ *Shashtika Shali Pinda Sweda* with *Balamoola* and *Dashamoola Kashaya* uses starch-rich rice, creating a hydrated interface over the skin similar to a starch-based transdermal system. The warm, moist application forms a semi-occlusive hydrated layer that softens the stratum corneum. *Swedana* induced vasodilatation increases local blood flow and skin permeability. This enhances transdermal absorption of medicaments from *Dashamoola kashaya*, *Balamoola Kashaya* and *Kshira*. The starch matrix allows gradual and sustained local release, comparable to controlled drug delivery. In Parsonage–Turner syndrome, this supports denervated and weakened muscles. *Shashtika Shali* provides *brmhana* due to its *snigdha* and *guru*

qualities. *Kshira* being amphipathic^[9], further facilitates penetration of therapeutic principles. The therapy reduces pain, muscle spasm, and prevents progressive muscle wasting.

✚ The *Nasya karma* especially exerts its effects on the *urdhvajatrugata pradasha*. *Nasa* is one among the *Pancha Jnanendriya* and is considered the *Dwara of Shiras*. After absorption of the drug, it acts on the diseases of *Skanda*, *Amsa*, and *Greeva* and the *doshas* are expelled from the *shira pradasha*. **“Tatra yaha snehanartham shunyashirasaam greevaaskandhoraa cha balajananartham”**. (*Su.Chi.40/22*) The absorption of the drugs is carried out in three media.

1. By general blood circulation, after absorption through the mucous membrane
2. By direct pooling into the venous sinuses of the brain via the inferior ophthalmic veins
3. By direct absorption into the cerebrospinal fluid^[7]

✚ *Nasapana* is defined as intake of medicine through *Nasamarga* a modification of *Nasya* where the *Aushadi* is instilled into the nostril is to be swallowed and it is mainly practiced in *Vatavyadhi*, specifically *Urdhwajatrugata Vyadhi*. *Nasapana* is a procedure that is predominantly used in *Jatruardhwa Vikara* like *Ardita*, *Pakshaghata*, *Vishwachi* and *Apabahuka*. *Chakradatta* mentions dose as same as *Kashaya Matra* for *Pana -Ipala*. But the appropriate dose has to be fixed on the patient's tolerance.

The formulation used in this case study is mentioned in *Chakradatta* – using *kashaya* of *Balamoola*, *Paribhadra*, *Atmagupta swarasa* and *Mamsarasa*. This particular formulation when used for one month in the form of *Nasapana* claims to benefit by producing *Vajrasamana Bahu*. In order to improve the efficacy of formulation and thereby benefit the patient, *Aja Sheersha Mamsa Rasa* was used in this case.^[8] The possible advantage of *Nasapana* over *Nasya* is the larger quantity of drug that can be administered and a longer period of contact which may have an added effect. With *Nasapana* one can achieve both *Shodhana* as well as *Shamana* action.

Apart from the small emissary veins entering the cavernous sinuses of the brain, a pair of venous branches emerging from the *alae nasi* will drain into the facial vein. These ophthalmic veins on the other hand also drain into the cavernous sinuses of the meninges, and in addition, neither the facial vein nor the ophthalmic veins have any valves. Therefore, there are more chances of the blood draining from the facial vein into the cavernous sinus in the lowered head position.

The momentary retention of the drug in the nasopharynx and the suction, causes oozing of the drug material into the air sinuses. These sites have rich blood vessels entering the brain and meninges through the existing

foramens in the bones. Therefore, there are better chances of drug transportation via this path.

CONCLUSION

Apabahuka corresponding to Parsonage–Turner syndrome represents a complex neuropathic condition affecting brachial plexus followed by muscle weakness and atrophy. The present case highlights the effectiveness of a comprehensive Panchakarma-based approach emphasizing *Brimhana*, *Snehana*, *Swedana*, and *Nasya/Nasapana* therapies in addressing *Dhatukshayajanya Vatavyadhi*. Panchakarma procedures played a crucial role in improving neuromuscular function, preventing further muscle wasting, and facilitating functional recovery. The observed clinical improvement suggests that Ayurvedic interventions, when applied with proper assessment, can serve as a valuable therapeutic option in conditions where conventional management offers limited benefit. However, larger clinical studies are warranted to substantiate these findings and establish standardized treatment protocols.

Declaration of patient consent

The patient has given his consent for reporting the case along with the images and other clinical information in the journal. The patient understands that his name and initials will not be published and due efforts will be made to conceal his identity.

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